

XMM-Newton: a pathfinder for future multi-wavelength and multi-messenger observations with Athena

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1 Introduction

This report is about the second deliverable of work package six (D6.2) of the EU funded XMM2Athena project, where we fitted an absorbed power law model and an absorbed black body model to all the sources of the 4XMM-DR11s catalogue, the catalogue of serendipitous sources from overlapping XMM-Newton observations [Traulsen et al. 2020], that have more than one extracted spectrum. We provide best-fit parameter values and confidence intervals. Of course, we could not achieve a good fit for all sources with spectra in the 4XMM-DR11s catalogue. All issues that we encountered during the fitting are described below and flagged in the catalogue. The report refers to the catalogue `xmm2athena_D6.2_V4.fits`.

2 Data and analysis

The 4XMM-DR11s catalogue contains 60720 sources with spectra in 135612 detections. 27640 sources have spectra in only one observation. For these sources the spectral information is already available in the first deliverable (D6.1), and hence they are not studied again here.

2.1 Preparing the data

From the first deliverable, where we fitted spectra of individual detections, we have information about merged spectra of the same detection in the same observation for the same instrument that we obtained using the SAS task *epicspeccombine*. This information allows us to exclude detections from this study, where the background spectrum of a least one detector has no counts, or where the net counts in at least one detector are less than zero. For the sources that are left with only one contributing detection after this step we already have the spectral information from the first deliverable. This means that we exclude a further 458 sources from this study, as there is either no or only one spectrum left after this step. The distribution of the remaining 32622 sources according to the number of contributing detections is shown in the left-hand panel of Fig. 1.

For these 32622 sources, we estimate a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) for the individual detections (adding the counts of pn and MOS in the full band), sort the detections according to decreasing SNR and derive a cumulative SNR for each detection, using it and all detections with an equal or higher SNR. For the 19081 sources that have only two contributing detections, we use both detections if the cumulative SNR increases when the second (lower SNR) spectrum is used (16959 sources), otherwise, only the first detection would be used (2122 sources). As the spectral properties of individual detections are covered by the first deliverable, we do not include these 2122 sources in this part.

We also exclude from this deliverable the 173 sources for which the detection with the highest individual SNR also has the highest cumulative SNR, since only one spectrum would contribute.

For the remaining sources with more than two contributing detections ($13541 - 173 = 13368$ sources), we introduce a selection criterion that is based on the relative range of the cumulative SNR, which is the range (maximum cumulative value minus maximum individual value) divided by the average. We are interested in identifying the detection where the relative range reaches its maximum (examples of plots of cumulative SNRs vs. individual SNRs are shown in Fig. 2). This will be the last detection that will be included in our spectral analysis of this source, together with all the detections that have a higher individual SNR than this last detection.

Since in some cases there is some “flickering” of the cumulative SNR, we have imposed a limit of >0.001 in the increase of the relative cumulative SNR, i.e., if the change in relative range between that last detection and the previous one (with a higher individual SNR) is ≤ 0.001 , the latter will be the new last detection to be used. For two sources, only one detection is left after this procedure, so we will also exclude these two sources from our study.

Figure 1: Distribution of the number of detections excluding detections that have no background counts or are background dominated (left panel) and of those included in the fits based on an SNR selection (details can be found in the text).

After the process outlined above, we are left with 30325 sources with at least two contributing detections (called the *Good sample*). We take all the contributing detections and make use of the XMM-Newton SAS task *epicspeccombine* to merge the spectra of all these detections for the same instrument. The distribution of the number of detections that are included in the fits is shown in the right-hand panel of Fig. 1. This means that we end up with at most one pn and one mos spectrum for each source. 19973 sources have spectra in both detectors, 7311 sources have only been observed with the pn detector and 3041 sources come solely from the MOS cameras. The distributions of background and net counts in the spectra after merging are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 2: Examples of the cumulative signal-to-noise ratio (Y axis) versus individual signal-to-noise ratio (X-axis).

Figure 3: Distribution of background counts (left panel) and net counts (right panel); after merging the spectra according to our selection procedure; see text) of the Good sample in the 0.2 - 12.0 keV band.

2.2 Fitting

As in the first deliverable the automated fits are done with python scripts that make use of the fitting and modelling software Sherpa 4.9.1 [Freeman et al., 2001] and the analysis software BXA [Bayesian X-ray Analysis; Buchner et al., 2014]. The spectra are binned to have at least 1 count per bin. We would need to model the source and background spectra simultaneously to preserve Poisson statistics. Actually, the fitting is performed in a two-step process. In the first step, we use a simple best fit method to fit the merged background spectra with an empirical background model (see Sect. 2.3.1) and save the best fit parameters. In the second step the fitting of the source + background spectra with fixed best-fit background parameters is done with BXA.

2.3 Spectral models

2.3.1 Background model

In the first part of this project, where we investigated spectra of individual detections, we did some tests to show that the empirical background model within BXA gives an acceptable description of the background and does not introduce any distortion in the source parameters. Therefore and to treat the spectra of the sources in the same way as the spectra of individual detections, we use again the implementation of the XMM-Newton empirical background model (originally developed by Richard Sturm at MPE [Maggi et al., 2014]) in the `bxa.sherpa.background` module.

This model has two parts. One part models the detector background and contains the contribution of lines and is not folded through the instrumental response. The second part accounts for emission of the cosmic X-ray background and X-ray emission of the local hot bubble and Galactic halo.

The background model, which is made up of a mixture of power laws, Gaussian lines and thermal emission components, is fitted in a multi-step process to the background spectrum with an increasing complexity of the model in each step,

and with the parameters of the previous steps constrained within a narrow range of the best-fit value obtained in the previous step. With this stepwise approach and thanks to the high number of background counts for most of the observations (see left panel of Fig. 3) the many free parameters of this model give acceptable fits.

We use a χ^2 test to estimate the goodness of fit of the background spectra. As almost all background spectra have a high number of counts (see left panel of Fig. 3), we bin the background spectra to at least 20 counts/bin and obtain p-values based on the χ^2 values and the number of effective parameters – which is 12 for pn and 7 for MOS – estimated in the first deliverable. For the very few cases (33 sources), where we had too few counts, we reduced the minimum number of counts per bin to 10 in the spectra of the corresponding detector. If this still gave us too few bins (pn background spectra of 6 sources), we reduced the number of effective parameters until we were able to estimate a p-value. These sources are flagged in the catalogue (in case we obtain a χ^2 p-value ≥ 0.01).

A χ^2 p-value ≥ 0.01 is considered as an acceptable fit. For detections that have spectra in both detectors and where the χ^2 p-value in one detector is below that limit while it is above in the other one, only the source spectrum of the latter detector is considered.

2.3.2 Source model

As source models we used an absorbed power law model and an absorbed blackbody model. We included the cflux model to derive the flux in the 0.2 to 12.0 keV band (cflux*TBabs*powerlaw or cflux*Tbabs*body in Xspec). In case the object is observed by both detectors, an inter-instrument normalisation constant is included. Free parameters are the logarithm of the hydrogen column density of the absorber, which is allowed to vary between 20 and 26 $\log_{10}(\text{cm}^{-2})$ for the power law model or between 18 and 26 $\log_{10}(\text{cm}^{-2})$ for the blackbody model, the power-law photon index, which can vary between 0 and 6 or the blackbody temperature, which can vary between 0.01 and 10 keV, the logarithm of the flux, which can vary between -7 and -17 $\log_{10}(\text{erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1})$, and the inter-instrument normalisation in all cases defined as MOS/pn which is constrained to be between 0 and 5. BXA requires the setting of a probability prior for each free parameter in the model. We used flat priors for all parameters within the limits stated above.

2.4 Best-fit parameters and error computation

The UltraNest algorithm implemented in BXA gives the marginalized posterior probability distribution for all free parameters in the fitted model. We used these distributions to estimate the best-fit parameters and the corresponding errors. For each free parameter we provide the median with percentiles of 5 and 95 per cent. We also provide the mode, calculated using a half sample algorithm [Robertson and Cryer, 1974] that makes use of functions from Henry Freudenriech (Hughes STX) statistics library (called ROBLIB) from AstroIDL User's Library, with the 90 per cent highest probability density interval (which corresponds to the narrowest interval that includes 90 per cent of the probability), calculated using Chen-Shao algorithm [Chen et al., 2000].

2.5 Goodness of fit

Since we have used Cash statistics for the fits and a large fraction of the spectra have less than 100 net counts, we have decided not to use χ^2 as a goodness-of-fit indicator. Cash maximum likelihood statistics lacks a direct estimate of goodness of fit (GoF). Therefore, we calculated the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) statistic between two cumulative distributions, and the corresponding p-value, as a quantitative estimate of the GoF. We note however that in this case the p-values for the KS statistic cannot be calculated the usual way. The cumulative distribution of the model depends on the parameters that were estimated from the data distribution. This implies that the two compared distributions are not independent. Nevertheless, we can do a permutation test to get an estimate of the p-value. For each source, we did 1000 resamplings, rearranging the original data+model sample in two equal-size subsamples, where the counts in each energy bin can come either from the data or the model sample, and estimate the corresponding KS statistic. Our estimated p-values are the fraction of resamplings that have statistics larger than the statistic of the original samples. Any model showing a KS p-value ≥ 0.01 is considered as an acceptable fit (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Distribution of the goodness-of-fit p-values for the fits to the source+background spectra with power law (left panel) and blackbody (right panel) model, respectively.

3 Results

In total the 4XMM-DR11s catalogue contains 60720 sources that have spectra. As explained above in section 2.1, we excluded all detections for which the automated definition of a background extraction region of at least one instrument [Webb et al., 2020] failed. Furthermore, we demand that a detection has more than 0 net counts in each contributing detector (pn and/or MOS). Based on the signal-to-noise ratio we decided which detections are included in the fit (see Sect. 2.1). Sources that have spectra in only one detection or that are left with only one detection after this selection procedure, are not covered by this study as

their properties have already been studied in the first deliverable. This leaves us with a *Good sample* of 30325 sources, which are investigated in this study.

4789 sources (16 per cent of the *Good sample*) gave formally unacceptable fits for the background model and a further 3661 sources (12.0 per cent) for the power law model or 11444 sources (38 per cent) for the blackbody model, respectively. Four sources are not included in the *Good fit sample*, as they have too few counts in the pn background spectra to obtain a χ^2 p-value with 10 counts per bin and 12 effective parameters (see Sect. 2.3.1). For 2643 sources the blackbody fit failed. Thus 23426 sources (77 per cent) remain within the *Good fit sample* with the power law model and 15352 sources (50 per cent) with the blackbody model.

Table 1: Overview of the number of detections in each sample. See Sect. 3 for the definition of the Good and Good fit samples.

	Power law	Blackbody	Both
	60720 (100%)		
Good sample	30325 (49.9%)		
Good fit sample	23426 (38.6%)	15352 (25.2 %)	14931 (24.4%)
Pointlike good fit sample	22839 (37.6%)	14880 (24.5%)	14480 (23.8%)

3.1 Description of the catalogues

3.1.1 Sources with spectra in 4XMM-DR11s

In total we provide three catalogues. The first one is a table that lists for each of the 60720 sources in the 4XMM-DR11s catalogue that have at least one spectrum the number of detections that are available and that remain after the selection procedure described in Sect. 2.1. In case only one detection is left, we provide the DETID from the 4XMM-DR11 catalogue that allows us to identify the detection in the catalogue of the first deliverable, to access its spectral properties. The columns of this table are the following:

SRCID: A unique identifier for each source, as in 4XMM-DR11s.

N_cat: The number of detections for which spectra are available.

N_good: The number of detections where all spectra have background counts and more than zero net counts.

N_fit: The number of detections used in the spectral fits. They are selected as described in Sect. 2.1.

DETID: A unique identifier for each detection, as in 4XMM-DR11.

3.1.2 Detections used in this deliverable

For all sources that have at least two spectra that contribute to our fits, we provide a second table that lists the DETIDs that are merged to do the fits. This table lists each source as many times as its number of detections. It contains the SRCIDs and DETIDs (see Sect. 3.1.1).

3.1.3 Catalogue of spectral properties

Our catalogue of spectral properties contains one row for each source, and 77 columns containing information about the source detection and the spectral-fitting results. Values that are not available are represented by an empty “nan” (or “null”) value. The first 13 columns contain information about the source, the following 57 columns contain information about the model fit (parameter values and confidence levels, flags and goodness of fit) and the last 7 columns correspond to source detection parameters and flags taken from 4XMM-DR11s .

Source

SRCID: A unique identifier, as in 4XMM-DR11s.

RA: The right ascension, as in 4XMM-DR11s.

DEC: The declination, as in 4XMM-DR11s.

LII: The longitude, as in 4XMM-DR11s.

BII: The latitude, as in 4XMM-DR11s.

The following set of columns is given for both the pn and MOS detectors that contribute to a source. If one of them does not contribute the values are set to “nan”. “*det*” can be “pn” or “MOS”.

det_cts: Number of total counts in the source extraction area.

det_bkgcts: Number of counts in the background extraction area.

det_netcts: Number of net counts in the source extraction area.

det_exp: Exposure time in seconds.

Model related columns

In the next 48 columns we give for both models, the power law and the blackbody model, for each of the four free parameters the median and mode with the corresponding lower and upper boundaries. Possible parameters names are: lgflux (logarithm of the flux in the 0.2 to 12.0 keV band, in units of log 10 (erg cm⁻² s⁻¹)), logNH (logarithm of the hydrogen column density of the absorber, in units of log 10 (cm⁻²)), PhoIndex (photon index), kT (blackbody temperature) and IIN (inter-instrument normalisation). *MO* indicates the model used, where “pl” stands for power law and “bb” for blackbody.

PARAMETER_med_*MO*: Median of the parameter value.

PARAMETER_med_min_*MO*, PARAMETER_med_max_*MO*: Percentiles of 5 and 95 per cent.

PARAMETER_mod_MO: Mode of the parameter value.

PARAMETER_mod_min_MO, PARAMETER_mod_max_MO: Lower and upper limits of the 90 per cent credible interval for the parameter.

Fitting statistics

dof: Degrees of freedom of the source fit.

pvalue_MO: KS p-value of the source+background fit for each model. "MO" can be "pl" (powerlaw) or "bb" (blackbody), respectively.

pval_bg_det: χ^2 p-value of the background fit for the pn and MOS detectors, if contributing. "det" can be "pn" or "MOS".

flag_MO: Flag for each model.

- 1: Negative or zero counts in the background extraction area;
- 2: Net counts below/equal to zero in the source extraction area;
- 3: Formally unacceptable background fit (pval_bkg_det < 0.01);
- 4: Formally unacceptable fit (pvalue < 0.01);
- 5: Too few background counts to obtain χ^2 p-values with fixed number of effective parameters;
- 6: BXA fit of the source+background spectrum failed;
- 0: None of the previous issues occurred.

det_there and det_use: Two flags indicating if a detector provides a spectrum for a source (det_there) and if it is used in the fitting (det_use). The entries are 0 for pn, 1 for MOS, and 2 for pn+MOS.

Source detection parameters and flags

is_ext: flag, with a value of 0 if EXTENT \leq 6 and 1 otherwise

EXTENT: Entries from the "EXTENT" column, as in 4XMM-DR11s.

EP_FLAG: Entries from the "EP_FLAG" column, as in 4XMM-DR11s.

PN_FLAG: Entries from the "PN_FLAG" column, as in 4XMM-DR11s.

M1_FLAG: Entries from the "M1_FLAG" column, as in 4XMM-DR11s.

M2_FLAG: Entries from the "M2_FLAG" column, as in 4XMM-DR11s.

SUM_FLAG: Entries from the "SUM_FLAG_4XMMDR11" column, as in 4XMM-DR11s

3.2 Fluxes

To get fluxes in the 0.2 to 12.0 keV band, we added the cflux component to our models. In case both instruments contribute spectra, the reported flux is the pn flux. A comparison of the flux obtained with the power law model and with the blackbody model is shown in Fig. 5. As can be seen from this figure there is a rather tight correlation between the fluxes obtained with these two models.

Figure 5: Correlation of the fluxes obtained with power law and blackbody model for the Good sample and the sample where both model give good fits (flag_pl and flag_bb are both 0) and the sources are pointlike (is_ext=0). The sources with very low lgflux_mod_pl correspond to source detection flags > 0 (most), pn only detections with negative net counts or low p-values of the spectral fit.

Figure 6 shows the relation between the mode of the logarithm of the flux derived from the spectra in the 0.2 to 12.0 keV band with the power law model with the logarithm of the EP_FLUX (0.2 – 12.0 keV) given in the 4XMM-DR11s catalogue for point-like sources ($is_ext=0$) of the *Good fit sample*. Also shown in Fig. 6 are plots of the flux-flux relation, where we indicate the photon index and hydrogen column density of the absorber obtained from our fits, respectively. Sources that deviate from the one-to-one correlation are those where the photon index or hydrogen column density differs significantly from the ones assumed in the 4XMM-DR11s catalogue. Furthermore, the fluxes from the source catalogue can include a contribution from detections for which no spectra have been extracted or that have not been included in our study.

Figure 6: Distribution of the fluxes obtained from power law spectral fits versus fluxes from the 4XMM-DR11s catalogue for point-like detections in the *Good fit sample*. The grey band in the upper panel contains 90 per cent of the detections. The two lower panels indicate the hydrogen column density (right) and photon index (left) obtained from the fit, respectively.

3.3 Inter-instrument normalisation

Already in our study of individual detections we found extreme values of the inter-instrument normalisation (above 2 or below 0.5) for about 5 per cent of the sources. We showed that several effects contribute to these extreme values, especially the `sum_flag` and `net counts`.

Here we obtain an inter-instrument normalisation above 2 or below 0.5 (in the following called “extreme cases”) for about 10 per cent of the *Good fit sample*,

independent of the source model (see Table 2 and Figure 7). We still observe a decrease of the extreme cases with count rate, which is stronger for the blackbody than for the power law model, but it is much less pronounced here than it was for individual detections in the first deliverable. In this study we do not only combine spectra of the two MOS instruments and fit spectra of different pn and MOS submodes simultaneously, but we also combine spectra of different observations. This can be a reason for the higher percentage of extreme cases and the reduced dependence on count rate.

We also show in Fig. 7 the normalised distributions of the modes of the inter-instrument normalisations for both models and the distribution of MOS/pn fluxes from the 4XMM-DR11s catalogue, for the Good fit sample common to the power law and blackbody models. It can be seen that they are not very different, showing that most of the dispersion is not due to our spectral fits.

Figure 7: Distribution of the inter-instrument normalisation modes obtained from spectral fits applying different filters for the power law (top left panel) and blackbody (top right panel) model. Normalised distribution inter-instrument normalisation for the power law model, blackbody model and MOS/pn flux ratio from 4XMM-DR11s, for the common Good fit sample between the power law model and the blackbody model.

A comparison of the IIN between power law and blackbody model is plotted in Fig. 8, showing that they are IIN for both models are similar for both models.

Table 2: Number of detections in different samples for all detections that have spectra in both instruments and for those where the inter-instrument normalisation is smaller than 0.5 or bigger than 2.0.

	Power law		Blackbody	
	IIN	IIN < 0.5 or IIN > 2.0	IIN	IIN < 0.5 or IIN > 2.0
Good fit sample	11701	703	7156	555
+flag =0 + netcts \geq 50	10681	510	6197	373
+flag =0 + netcts \geq 100	8544	268	4693	210

Figure 8: Correlation of the inter-instrument normalisation obtained with the power law and blackbody models for the sample where both model give good fits and the sources. The sources away from the 1:1 relation in the bottom left all have very low $kT=0.01-0.03$.

3.4 Spectral parameters

For the discussion below we have cross-correlated our Good sample with the SIMBAD [Wenger et al. 2000] database, based the 4XMM-DR11s source positions and a circular area of radius 5 arcsec, using the xmatch CDS service and TOPCAT [Taylor 2005].

Power law model: distribution of the best fit values of the photon index and the column density

We show in Fig. 9 the distribution of the best fit values for the column density N_H (top left) and the photon index Γ (top right). We also show N_H versus Γ (bottom right): it is clear that most sources are in a vertical band around $\Gamma \sim 1-3$, but there is a well populated “branch” of sources towards the right with a slight angle. Looking at the SIMBAD identifications (bottom right), it is clear that this branch is mostly populated by Galactic stars and some galaxies. We believe that the branch is caused by trying to fit thermal emission with an absorbed power law.

Figure 9: Distributions of the best fit values of the logarithm of the column density ($\log N_H$) and the photon index ($\text{PhoIndex}_{\text{mod}}$) for the power law model, for the good sample and the Good fit power law sample of pointlike sources. Top left: distribution of $\log N_H$. Top right: distribution of $\text{PhoIndex}_{\text{mod}}$. Bottom left: $\log N_H$ versus $\text{PhoIndex}_{\text{mod}}$ with the “branch” delimited by grey lines (see text). Bottom right: $\log N_H$ versus $\text{PhoIndex}_{\text{mod}}$ with colours for different types of sources.

Blackbody model: distribution of the best fit values of the temperature and the column density

We show in Fig. 10 the distribution of the best fit values for the column density N_H (top left) and the temperature kT (top right). The latter has been truncated at $kT=3$ keV for clarity, there are some values all the way up to $kT=6$ keV, but they only correspond to 0.65% of the total number of values. We also show N_H versus kT (bottom right): the sources appear to concentrate in a lower cloud ($\log N_H < 20$, $kT \sim 0.1-1.6$) an upper cloud ($\log N_H > 20$, $kT > 0.1$) and a dense sinuous “branch” that grows vertically between $\log N_H \sim 20$ and 23, keeping to $kT < 0.4$. Looking at the SIMBAD identifications (bottom right), AGN populate mostly the lower cloud, stars dominate the branch and the upper cloud, and galaxies are mostly in the

Figure 10: Distributions of the best fit values of the logarithm of the column density ($\log N_H_{\text{mod}}$) and the temperature (kT_{mod}) for the blackbody model, for the good sample and the Good fit blackbody sample of pointlike sources. Top left: distribution of $\log N_H$. Top right: distribution of kT (truncated at 3 keV). Bottom left: $\log N_H$ versus kT . Bottom right: $\log N_H$ versus kT with colours for different types of sources.

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